

LASER IONISATION AND SPECTROSCOPY OF ACTINIDES

Grant Agreement No: 861198

Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) Innovative Training Network (ITN)

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Report on the creation of the LISA promotional material

D27 – Promotional Material

Document identifier:	LISA-D27-Identity-Promotional Material_Draft
Due date of deliverable:	December 2020
Justification for delay:	[if delays occurred]
Report release date:	30/12/2020
Work package:	WP7: Outreach, Dissemination, and Communication
Lead beneficiary:	CERN
Document status:	Draft

Abstract

The *Strategy and Graphical Identity* for LISA (Laser Ionisation and Spectroscopy of Actinides) details the strategic aspects of the project's communications to help determine its identity/voice, as well as the graphic identity. On a first stage, it supported the creation of *promotional material* destined to represent the LISA network at national and international events, developed with the support of CERN Design Service and EU Communication Officer at CERN, following an editorial and design process in sequence.

LISA ITN, 2020

For more information on the project, partners and contributors please see: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

This Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) Innovative Training Network (ITN) receives funding from the European Union H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement no. 861198. LISA will run from November 2019 to October 2023.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Daniela Antonio [EU Communication Officer]	CERN	06/12/2020
Edited by	Isabelle Fontaine [Project Officer]	CERN	16/11/2020
Reviewed by	Daniela Antonio [EU Communication Officer] Isabelle Fontaine [Project Officer] Bruce Marsh [Scientific coordinator]	CERN	01/12/2020
Approved by	Bruce Marsh [Scientific coordinator] Steering Committee	CERN Consortium	dd/mm/yy

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. HOW TO USE THIS DOCUMENT	4
2. IDENTITY	4
2.1. ABOUT THE PROJECT	5
2.2. GRAPHIC IDENTITY	5
3. STRATEGY	6
3.1. COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES	6
3.2. AUDIENCES	6
3.3. CHANNELS	6
3.4. KEY MESSAGES	6
3.5. BRANDING AND TEMPLATES.....	8
4. PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL.....	8
4.1. PHASE 1 – EDITABLE MATERIALS	8
4.1.1. <i>Newsletter headers</i>	8
4.1.2. <i>Social Media</i>	10
4.1.3. <i>Business cards</i>	10
4.1.4. <i>Beach flag</i>	10
4.2. PHASE 2 – STATIC MATERIALS	11
4.2.1. <i>Roll-up</i>	11
4.2.2. <i>Brochure</i>	11
5. CONCLUSION/SUMMARY	13
ANNEX I: ROLL-UP	14
ANNEX II: BROCHURE	15

Executive Summary:

The *Strategy and Graphic Identity* for the LISA (Laser Ionisation and Spectroscopy of Actinides) project, developed under *M30 – Branding and Design*, details the strategic aspects of the project's communications – goals, audiences, channels – to help determine its identity/voice and graphic identity to support the LISA internal and external communication activities. On a first stage, this strategy and graphic identity supported the creation of the promotional material (*D27 – Promotional Material*) meant to promote the LISA network at national and international conferences, workshops, exhibitions, and trade fairs. Each Beneficiary, Partner, ESR and WP has been consulted through the Steering Committee, making sure the LISA network, its research and philosophy are adequately represented in these materials.

Both the work developed under *M30 – Branding and Design* and *D27 – Promotional Material* have been developed with the support of CERN Design Service and the EU Communication Officer at CERN, following an editorial and design process in sequence. While public, this document is meant for internal use and as a tool to insure impactful communication by Early Career Researchers (ESRs) and the LISA project team.

1. HOW TO USE THIS DOCUMENT

In order to properly create the LISA promotional material, it was first needed to determine the strategic aspects of the project's communications – goals, audiences, channels, and key messages – to help determine its identity/voice and graphic identity to support the LISA internal and external communication activities, resulting in the *Strategy and Graphical Identity* (Section 2) for the LISA project.

In the future, when creating any content related to the project, both the conceptual and graphic identity should be respected, so as to present a coherent image to the different key audiences and to support the network of Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) in conducting the communication activities. As an example, the strategic and graphic identity were first used to create promotional materials, in particular the related briefings: the description of the project, audiences and key messages were used to create imagery, symbols and editorial content for all the materials, from the logo to the brochure introducing the project. The promotional materials is meant to promote the LISA network at national and international events. Each Beneficiary, Partner, ESR and WP coordinator has been consulted through the Steering Committee, making sure the LISA network, its research and philosophy are adequately represented in these materials.

This document is meant as a tool to insure an impactful communication by the network of ESRs and the LISA project team. Therefore, while the description of the project's communication activities is final, the details related to their operationalisation might be later updated as ESRs combine theory and practice.

2. IDENTITY

In this section, we describe the project's conceptual identity (2.1), as well as the graphic aspects to implement in all materials produced for the project and the templates prepared to support the network in their reporting responsibilities (2.2). While not, strictly speaking, related to *D27 – Promotional Material*, and rather *M30 – Branding and Design*, this section was thought out to facilitate consistency in the project's communications.

2.1. ABOUT THE PROJECT

The LISA (Laser Ionisation and Spectroscopy of Actinides) consortium aims to train a new generation of experts in laser-related research, whilst they work towards the goal of vastly improving our understanding of the atomic and nuclear properties of the chemical elements known as the actinides. This will include the theoretical study of the atomic structure of trans-actinide and super heavy elements, the development of new laser technologies to enable the planned experimental study of these atoms with unprecedented sensitivity and precision, and the extraction of the underlying fundamental atomic and nuclear properties. Finally, LISA aims to exploit these techniques and the isotopes themselves, for applications within the medical and environmental sectors; as well as offer this opportunity to other communities, such as the energy sector.

The LISA research is an essential prerequisite for unravelling the structure of the super-heavy elements at the end of Mendeleev's table, but the value of this activity extends far beyond the fields of fundamental atomic and nuclear Physics research. In-depth knowledge of the nuclear properties of an isotope and the atomic properties of the element are precursors for understanding their practical applications and crucial to their identification and handling. Immediate valorisation of these findings will be sought out in the fields of radioecology, nuclear medicine and, ultimately, waste management from nuclear power production. These fields are of utmost importance in our society, namely for the treatment of distributed cancers (metastasis), the deadliest and most difficult to address; for the study of the consequences of our activities on the environment; and for assessing and addressing our accumulating nuclear waste.

LISA researchers will be immersed in an international and inter-sectorial environment with broad and interdisciplinary training: atomic theory, laser technology, atomic and nuclear structure; advanced computing for simulation, calculations and big data analysis; hardware design, vacuum technology, computer programming for equipment control and data acquisition. A suite of soft-skills training, including business and communication among others, will equip the ESRs with the tools and experience necessary to maximize both their employability and their ability to transfer their acquired know-how in their future endeavours.

2.2. GRAPHIC IDENTITY

Please see below a list of graphic materials available to the network.

- **Logo**, available in project's collaborative workspace. *Please contact the Project Office.*
- **Image gallery**, available in project's collaborative workspace. *Please contact the Project Office.*
- **Colours**
 - White: HTML/HEX: #EFF2E3; RGB (239, 242, 227)
 - Yellow: HTML/HEX: #FBEA1C; RGB(251, 234, 28)
 - Red: HTML/HEX: #e5352b; RGB(229, 43, 53)
 - Green: HTML/HEX: #2eac68; RGB(46, 172, 104)
 - Blue: HTML/HEX: #253366; RGB(37, 51, 102)
 - Black: HTML/HEX: #1C211C RGB(38, 33, 28)

See also the technical sheet for the logo [here](#) (collaborative workspace).

- **Font type**
 - **Reports: Titles:** Tahoma 12pt, *Body:* Calibri 11pt
 - **Graphic materials, including logo:** Monserrat, available [here](#).

3. STRATEGY

The following section details the six pillars of strategic communication: objectives, audience, channels, key messages, key activities, including digital communication activities. Some extra material will be linked where appropriate, with the goal of making the network of ESRs independent in their communications.

3.1. COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

- Implement and maintain effective communication among the project participants
- Engage the wider scientific community with the project developments
- Engage the public with beam research and its applications
- Demonstrate the impact of the project to the public and policy makers

3.2. AUDIENCES

The following table describes the project’s audiences.

This information should be complemented with section 3.4 Key Messages.

Audience	Information needs	Drivers
Project participants	Project information Updates on results and plan	Community spirit Career development
Scientific community	Main advancements Collaboration opportunities	Scientific excellence Peer recognition
Industry	Potential knowledge transfer opportunities	Innovation Job creation
Decision-makers	Summary of the results Societal impact of project	Scientific excellence Economic/societal impact
Public	Societal impact	Curiosity Impact

3.3. CHANNELS

The following diagram details the channels available for the project’s communications.

These are the channels each Beneficiary, Partner, ESR and WP coordinator should follow.

3.4. KEY MESSAGES

The following table details the key messages to address each audience. More detailed messages could be added as the project progresses. For more information and an example, see: [CERN Communication Strategy](#)

AUDIENCE	DRIVERS	KEY MESSAGES ¹
Project participants	Community spirit Career development	LISA attracts some of the most talented young people in the world. LISA aims to train the next-generation of scientists, technicians and engineers. Education within the LISA-ITN is an excellent prerequisite for a successful career in industrial R&D.
Scientific community	Scientific excellence Peer recognition Funding	CERN, the organisation coordinating LISA, is at the forefront of particle physics and technology. LISA partners comprise an international network. The project is full of opportunities for networking and collaborations. Collaborations like LISA are models for grass-roots, distributed, large-scale approaches to big science.
Industry	Innovation Job creation Collaboration	LISA combines expertise in industrial development with science, providing the base for a career in industrial R&D. LISA inspires and trains the future workforce. The unique know-how within LISA is key to bridge the gap between fundamental research and its applications. Cooperation between industry and science within the LISA-ITN help to accelerate industrial innovation.
Decision-makers	Scientific excellence Economic/societal impact	LISA participants are some of the world's leading centres for physics, producing cutting-edge science and technology. Projects like LISA open new possibilities for career development for young researchers.
Public	Curiosity Societal impact	CERN has built and runs some of the largest scientific instruments in the world. Fundamental research in the LISA context will contribute to deepen physicists' knowledge about the heaviest elements of the Universe, casting a light on... LISA scientific and technological developments have the potential to have meaningful impact on society.

¹ Based on: *CERN's Communications Strategy 2017-2020*: [CERN Communication Strategy](#), selected by the EU Communication Officer at CERN, Daniela Antonio, and revised by the Steering Committee.

3.5. BRANDING AND TEMPLATES

Daniela Antonio, the Communication Officer for the [EU Projects Office at CERN](#) was consulted to establish the branding of the network and define a strategy for the communication activities. The work included the creation of templates for reporting as detailed below, leading to the conclusion of *M30 – Branding and Design*. These materials were delivered together with those produced for *D27 – Promotional Material*.

- Report template (.DOCX)
- Press release template (.DOCX)
- Events poster template (.PPTX)
- PowerPoint presentation template (.PPTX)
- Business cards (.PNG)
- Signature banner (.PNG)
- Social Media template (.PNG)
- Newsletter header (.PNG)

Find all files in SharePoint. *Please contact the Project Office.*

4. PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

The promotional material listed below has been created in order to promote the LISA network at national and international conferences, workshops, exhibitions, and trade fairs, comprising an events kit for project participants. Each Beneficiary, Partner, ESR, and WP has been consulted through the Steering Committee to offer a global view of the LISA network, its research and philosophy. The materials have been developed with the support of EU Communication Officer at CERN and the CERN Design Service, together with the Graphic Identity (Section 2.2) previously introduced, following an editorial and design process in sequence.

The CERN Design team was provided with precise information on the LISA team's expectations. In addition, the following key words and imagery, summarizing LISA project, were provided for inspiration: international network, partnerships, research, innovation, nuclear world, laser, atoms, radioecology and nuclear medicine.

4.1. PHASE 1 – EDITABLE MATERIALS

The logo was delivered and approved in August 2020. On a first stage, the designer (Melissa Perrey) was asked to produce the editable materials listed in section 4.1, with their first proposal (delivered in October 2020) having been accepted by the LISA Management Team, including one header proposal for each newsletter; three proposals (one abstract + two with a photo option) for social media banners; two proposals for Business Cards, of which one was selected; and two propositions for beach flags.

4.1.1. Newsletter headers

CERN Design Team was given information on the two types of newsletters (annual for the scientific community and decision-makers – *LISA Annual Newsletter*; quarterly for the LISA network – *LISA Bulletin*), namely: the target audiences, content (title, logo and design element), project's expectations and needs (user-friendly, adaptable newsletters for different issues, i.e without time identifiers, news identifiers, etc.). The designer delivered both the materials and the newsletters' graphic identity (colour scheme, font type).

The quarterly newsletter will facilitate internal communications by reporting to all members of the network (scientist, administrator, or ESR) on the progress of the different work packages and the status of milestones and deliverables. It will be curated by the network of ESRs, with the feedback/support of an editorial board.

Figure 1. Quarterly newsletter header.

The annual newsletter that will be edited by the active members of WP7 with the support of ESRs, reporting on the progress and achievements of the whole network. This newsletter will be distributed to the scientific community and policy makers (e.g. national funding agencies) to highlight the general progress of the research field, opportunities for collaboration and the project's scientific, technological and societal impact.

Figure 2. LISA annual newsletter header.

For both these examples, EU acknowledgement as mandated by the Grant Agreement will be included in the body of the newsletter, rather than the header itself. For an example, visit: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

4.1.2. Social Media

The LISA network will establish its presence on social media of professional and public nature. Contribution to the different social media will be made by the ESRs and coordinated by one of them. Two training sessions have been given by the EU Communication Officer at CERN (find the presentations on Indico). To ensure a coherent image, two social media cards have been designed in an editable format (Figure 3); the LISA team requested the design to be adaptable to different social networks, to include EU acknowledgement.

Figure 3. Two templates for the creation of social media posts for LISA channels.

4.1.3. Business cards

The LISA business cards serve the usual purpose of business cards, being meant for LISA network members, ESRs and the LISA management team to share at conferences, exhibitions, open days, events, etc.; they have the added benefit of promoting LISA among networks of interest to the project. The LISA team requested all of the fields included in the card (as shown in Figure 4), as well as the logo and EU acknowledgment.

Figure 4. Two sides of the LISA business card for ESRs, provided in an editable .PPTX format.

4.1.4. Beach flag

Two beach flag mockups were proposed by the CERN Design Service. As both fit the expectations of the LISA team quite well, it was decided to produce both to include in the LISA events kit (Figure 5), available to project

participants to promote LISA at national and international events, for example, flagging a LISA stand in exhibitions or the registration desk at LISA internal events.

Figure 5. Two versions of the LISA beach flag.

4.2. PHASE 2 – STATIC MATERIALS

On a second phase, the CERN Design Team was requested to support the production of a roll up, brochure and poster template; the latter was meant to announce the LISA events in a cohesive way throughout the project. The LISA team, with the support of the EU Communication Officer at CERN and Jake Johnson, Early Stage Researcher in the LISA network, created the editorial content for each material type. The final version of these materials was delivered in December 2020, before the submission of the present report.

4.2.1. Roll-up

The purpose of the roll-up would be to address the community at national and international events, highlighting key aspects about the LISA network, inviting further exploration of the website and LISA-related content. It was requested that the template would match the structure used at events, with the dimensions of 100x200 cm. All the content, including all beneficiaries and partners logos, was delivered to the CERN Design Team in October 2020. For the unformatted content and a mock-up, see ANNEX I: ROLL-UP ANNEX I: ROLL-UP.

4.2.2. Brochure

To produce the brochure was a project in itself, involving several contributors and the entire consortium in providing feedback to the content created, ensuring its match to the LISA goals and key messages. The LISA Project Office, together with the EU Communication Officer at CERN and Jake Johnson, one of the LISA ESRs, created the editorial content, providing a detailed briefing to the designer, as shown in ANNEX 2: BROCHURE.

Unsurprisingly, after a first iteration delivered in November 2020, the brochure require some additional work, thus delaying both the submission of the present report and the completion of *D27 – Promotional Material*.

The final mock-up can be seen in Figure 6 (*recto*) and Figure 7 (*verso*).

Figure 6. Mock-up of the brochure, front-side.

Figure 7. Mock-up of the brochure, back-side.

5. CONCLUSION/SUMMARY

The work to complete *M30 – Branding and Design* and *D27 – Promotional Material* started in March 2020 with the support of the EU Projects Office at CERN. Due to the complexity of actors involved, the work was concluded nearly three-quarters of a year later, leaving the project with a complete events pack, press pack and, generally speaking, a promotional pack, available to the entirety of the consortium for the promotion of the LISA network. More materials will be added with the progression of the project and the communication activities of ESRs (including newsletters, social media, public outreach, etc.). More information about the project’s activities and how the present report will support them can be found in [Communication Strategy and Plan of Activities](#), presented at the LISA Mid-term Review on 26 November 2020.

ANNEX I: ROLL-UP

Title: LISA

Subtitle: Shining light on the heaviest elements

15 early stage researchers working with **24 institutions**, coming together in **one network**, the LISA Network.

We strive to better understand the heaviest elements using laser-based techniques

We link industrial partners to research institutions

We want to share our knowledge through outreach and education

Subtitle: We study:

- Atomic structure
- Laser performance
- Nuclei of rare heavy elements

Subtitle: We aim to:

- Understand challenging nuclear and atomic structure models
- Produce of radio-isotopes for medicine
- Trace analysis of radio-isotopes in the environment

Subtitle: We work to develop:

- Radioactive ion beam facilities
- Wavelength-tuneable laser technology
- Experimental methods
- Theoretical modelling software

Subtitle: Get involved

- Do you work in the same fields as LISA? >> Follow the network's scientific results!
- Do you want to gain research experience with LISA? >> Follow our upcoming training events!
- Are you interested in science? >> Look out for our upcoming outreach events!

More information: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch #LISA ITN

[Icons] Facebook | Twitter | Instagram | Youtube

Acknowledgement:

[Picture](#) This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 861198.

Figure 8. Mock-up of the roll-up produced by the CERN Design Team, content provided by the LISA team and EU Communication Officer at CERN.

ANNEX II: BROCHURE

PAGE 1 (OUTSIDE): COVER (SEE OUTLINE)

PAGE 2 (INSIDE): A WORD FROM...

Title: A word from...

Subtitle: Bruce Marsh, LISA Project Coordinator

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#)

Hosted by a consortium of world-leading research groups, laboratories and industrial partners, fifteen Early-Stage Researchers will use and develop state-of-the-art experimental and theoretical techniques to explore the applications of actinide elements and associated technologies, for the scientific community and beyond the laboratory. They will develop new tools and methods for laser ionization and spectroscopy, and bridge the gap between science, industry and society to push the boundaries of knowledge and discover new applications of the often-elusive actinides, the heaviest elements of the periodic table.

Highlight: “ESRs will develop new techniques to push the boundaries of knowledge and discover new applications of the often-elusive actinides, the heaviest elements of the periodic table.”

Subtitle: Thomas Cocolios, LISA Training Officer

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#)

The LISA Network will train a new generation of engineers and scientists ready to tackle the challenges of tomorrow. Our fifteen Early-stage Researchers will develop their skills through their participation in cutting-edge research projects performed at leading scientific institutions and state-of-the-art high-tech industries. A blend of network-wide training events, advanced courses at each academic institution, and inter-sectorial secondments will strengthen the links between academic, research and industrial partners, ensuring a comprehensive training that will maximise the employability of the trainees.

We are open to welcoming additional young researches as affiliates to the network. We will endorse their participation in training events and network activities through our PhD label.

Subtitle: Korbinian Hens, Hubner Photonics (Industrial Partner)

The LISA Network wants to prepare trainees to carry out the transfer of knowledge and ideas into real-world products and services that can tackle challenges shared by academy and industry. In this sense, the purpose of the LISA Network is perfectly aligned with the vision of Hubner Photonics, which is striving to increase the availability of the type of laser-based equipment that contributes to an improved quality of life and a better environment.

Logos: [See folder](#)

PAGE 3 (INSIDE): ACTINIDE RESEARCH

Title: Researching actinides, the heaviest elements

Subtitle: Producing actinides

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#) *The MEDICIS robot loads a target to produce radioisotopes.*

There are two current routes to produce short-lived actinides and transactinide elements: the spallation of other very heavy elements, and fusion-based reactions. For the first, LISA will investigate new approaches for the development of actinide ion beams, such as volatile-molecule extraction, followed by laser-induced breakup and resonance ionization at Isotope Separator On-line (ISOL) facilities. The application of expertise held by the LISA consortium in radioactive ion beam production and purification will be crucial in expanding the inventory of ISOL beams in the elusive actinide region of the nuclear chart.

For the other, the LISA consortium is active in the use and development of all of the state-of-the-art variations of the fusion-based processes. New approaches will be explored to improve the beam intensity, efficiency, and resolution of the techniques: higher primary beam intensities, ink-jet deposition to produce novel targets, and high-definition gas catcher components.

Subtitle: Developing atomic spectroscopy

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#) *Peering into atomic orbitals with lasers.*

With the advent of tuneable lasers, today it is possible to perform high-resolution spectroscopy of atomic structures and identify single energy levels of strongly correlated electrons in the atomic shell. The importance of relativistic effects renders calculations in these systems particularly complex.

The state-of-the-art approaches that allow high-level treatment of actinides and superheavy elements are the relativistic-coupled cluster (CC), configuration interaction (CI) approaches, and multi-configuration Dirac-Fock (MCDF) approaches. The development of the coupled cluster approach (High sector Fock space coupled cluster) within the LISA project will extend the applicability of this method and improve its accuracy by an order of magnitude.

Experimentally, higher resolution can be achieved by refining the existing techniques. For example, the study of atomic systems at CERN is possible with resonance ionization spectroscopy performed at the CRIS experiment, while the study of photodetachment of radioactive ion beams of negative ions is possible with the GANDALPH experiment. Within LISA, we will couple GANDALPH and CRIS to create a one-of-a-kind, multi-purpose laser spectroscopy apparatus to bring about the photodetachment measurements of the most exotic actinides within reach.

Title: Exploring nuclear structure

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#) *Cutting-edge setups explore exotic nuclei.*

The lack of fundamental ground-state nuclear structure data in the actinide region and beyond is a testament to the challenges faced with such isotopes, such as low production rates that require extremely sensitive experimental set-ups. Innovation within LISA will enable the systematic investigation of the evolution of nuclear structure properties, like spin, charge radii and electromagnetic moments in the heaviest elements: the sensitivity of the charge radii to octupole deformation in the actinide isotopes with mid-shell neutron numbers will be explored and the charge radii measurements of nobelium will be extended to known isomeric states in the region. Such experimental data will support our understanding of super energetic events, such as the recently observed neutron star mergers.

Title: Developing laser technologies

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#) *Lasers measure tiny atomic shifts due to nuclear structure.*

The LISA activities require a range of industrial and scientific laser solutions. Over recent years, groups within the LISA Network have built strong links with the industrial sector and they are at the forefront of establishing the use of high-reliability industrial solid-state lasers for scientific purposes.

The consortium will allow researchers and industrial partners to jointly develop the pulse-amplified research Ti:Sapphire laser into a commercial-grade product, greatly improving its ease of use and reliability, facilitating its adoption for a vast range of uses beyond the immediate scope of the network. Furthermore, the turnkey 'C-Wave' laser from Hubner Photonics will be adapted to the needs of the laser spectroscopy community with the help of Lioptec, one of the industrial partners. Both of these new laser systems will be characterised and validated with a real-world test at the world's most sensitive collinear laser spectroscopy experiments at the LISA research partner facilities. CERN will promote these high-tech LISA developments and form the hub of LISA for knowledge transfer.

PAGE 4 (INSIDE): LISA FOR SOCIETY

Title: LISA for society

The societal impact of LISA will require the group of Early Stage Researchers to apply their understanding of the core topics of the network beyond the realms of fundamental research, namely in nuclear medicine and radioecology; and to share it with the wider community.

Medical: The LISA Network will investigate the production of ^{225}Ac for medical applications. This isotope has great prospects in the treatment of distributed cancers, the deadliest and most difficult to treat. The supply of ^{225}Ac currently relies on limited reserves from twentieth-century nuclear stockpiles, which are being decommissioned and thus inaccessible. By implementing the LISA laser technology at research facilities, high-purity samples of ^{225}Ac can be delivered for medical research in Europe. The technology will be stringently tested towards the next generation ISOL facilities, where this isotope could be produced in sufficient quantities for patient care.

Environmental: The actinides are so rare in the environment that their presence is usually a sign of a nuclear incident. Monitoring systems rely on the detection of the tiniest amounts. Moreover, the relative distribution of these actinides is a clear indicator of their origin. The proposed developments with the LISA project will allow the fast simultaneous measurement of all major actinides, which will strongly improve the current time-consuming practice of sequential measurements and help refining the entire monitoring process.

Outreach: The members of the LISA Network are committed to public engagement and the dissemination of knowledge to a wider audience to promote a positive image of nuclear research. LISA will build on that experience and share its impact across social media and knowledge dissemination platforms such as Scholarpedia (www.scholarpedia.org), as well as regular events at local high schools, tours of cutting-edge facilities, and events like the laboratories' Open Days or Researchers' Night.

[2nd column]

Title: Getting involved

Subtitle: Training and Education

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#) *We value training researchers and sharing our work.*

Researchers interested in the work of LISA can easily get involved by following one of the training events, on themes from actinide production, to nuclear structure, to computational techniques.

Subtitle: PhD Label

Picture: [\(LINK\)](#) *Research associated with the Network at JGU.*

For those looking to benefit in greater depth from the LISA network there is the LISA PhD label, open to PhD students who perform research related to the activities of the network. The label is given to researchers who participate in at least three events organised by the Training Office, show mobility and internationalisation in their training and research profile, and contribute to the science communication strategy of the LISA network.

Candidates for the PhD Label may participate in all events under the same conditions as the ESRs, gain access to additional training opportunities proposed within the LISA network, and get support from the LISA Training Office in defining and following up on their training. Moreover, they get to network with all the ESRs, as well as with our Beneficiaries and Partners across Europe and the world.

PAGE 5 (OUTSIDE, END): TIMELINE

Title: Recent scientific and technical highlights in actinide research

Timeline call: 2016

Subtitle: Atom-at-a-time laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of nobelium

A foray into the unknown atomic structures of transfermium elements: for the first time, ultra-rare Nobelium was studied by laser resonance ionisation. The spectacular sensitivity of the experimental set-up allowed the structure of the outer shells to be probed, defying even the most sophisticated theoretical models.

Timeline call: 2017

Subtitle: High-resolution laser spectroscopy of long-lived plutonium isotopes

Low production cross section, nuclear instability, and minimal current knowledge of optical transitions: these massive challenges, often associated with heavy element studies, were overcome with the first collinear laser spectroscopy of Plutonium, the heaviest element thus far studied with this method.

Timeline call: 2018

Subtitle: Characterization of the shape-staggering effect in mercury nuclei

Laser ionisation spectroscopy was used to probe the fascinating region of neutron deficient mercury, where huge jumps in charge radius are seen when successively removing neutrons from the nucleus. The results, coupled with state-of-the-art Monte Carlo shell model calculations, cut to the heart of the fifty-year-old problem. The nature of the jumps are now understood as a critical phenomenon of a quantum phase transition.

Timeline call: 2019

Subtitle: The LISA Network is born

Ideas were refined, the partner institutes came together, and the word was out for young researchers to join in on exciting developments in the study of actinides.

Timeline call: 2020

Subtitle: The electron affinity of astatine

The electron affinity of astatine was determined using laser photodetachment spectroscopy. Knowledge of this fundamental chemical property now paves the way for its use in Targeted Alpha

Treatment of certain cancers, and provides a benchmark for theoretical models, whose output must be refined to match the new observations, revealing the extent to which quantum and relativistic effects play a role in atomic structure. The developed technique opens the door for similar studies on even heavier elements: the actinides.

Timeline call: From 2020

Subtitle: The era of LISA actinide study

The ESRs begin their work on the laser ionisation and spectroscopy of actinides, with the hopes of populating the timeline with more highlights in years to come. These highlights are the beginning of a new chapter in actinide research. They pave the way for a deeper and more complete understanding of the structures of some of the most exotic elements, and the group of LISA ESRs will collaborate to develop sensitive experimental techniques and accurate theoretical models.

PAGE 5 (OUTSIDE, MIDDLE): A FEW HIGHLIGHTS

Title: Heavy elements are...

Picture: (LINK) Radioisotope	Picture: (LINK) Nuclear Clock	Picture: (LINK) Astatine
Subtitle: CHANGING SOCIETY	Subtitle: CHANGING WHAT IS POSSIBLE	Subtitle: DIFFICULT TO GET HOLD OF
0.05	470 billion	0.00007
mass in micrograms of a radioisotope used for a Targeted Alpha Therapy Treatment	years would pass before a Thorium nuclear clock would lose a second	mass of naturally occurring astatine in the Earth's crust in kg
130000	2	30x10 ²¹
mass in micrograms of the active molecule used for a chemotherapy treatment	years pass before a quartz clock loses a second	mass of the rest of the Earth's crust in kg

Subtitle: Credits & Acknowledgement

LISA

Contributors: Thomas Elias Cocolios, Jake Johnson, Bruce Marsh

Editor: Jake Johnson

Coordination: Isabelle Fontaine

With special thanks to: Early Stage Researchers, Beneficiaries and Partners

CERN

EU Projects Office: Daniela Antonio, EU Communication Officer

Graphic Design Service: Melissa Loyse Perrey, Graphic Designer